

Original Research Article

Knowledge and Perception of Mothers towards Child Sexual Abuse

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Abstract

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Child sexual abuse is an incident that affects a child vigorously, taking advantage of victims who are unable to give their consent. In this action, the abuser violates the rules or social prohibitions of society. Child violence is one of the most significant social issues impacting children. Child abuse is described as the expected injury to the child. It has been a matter of competent communal concern for decades. Physical and sexual acts were the most widely recognized abuses of the early period. Child sexual abuse (CSA) is a universal communal criminal. In this act there is no involvement of a child or the child are unable to give consent about this act as they do not understand the maltreatment that they are facing at some instant. According to World Health Organization below the age of 18 years 150 million girls and 73 million boys faced sexual violence during their life. The ratio of violence is higher among girls than boys. Incidence is higher among women than among male children. This study indicates 36% female and 29% males have been sexually abused in their childhood. Mothers play a vital role in the success of the sensitivity directive in their children, especially in younger ages. Nearly 50 percent of mothers of sexually abused children claim that they have been sexually maltreated as children. The purpose of the research is to evaluate the mother's awareness and understanding of child sexual exploitation. Assess mothers' awareness and understanding of child sexual exploitation. Finding a connection between mothers' awareness and the selected baseline results. The quantitative descriptive cross-sectional research design is used to perform this study. Questionnaire was used to collect the data. The questionnaires were administered by using convenient sampling. Data were statistically analyzed by descriptive criteria on SPSS version 21 and inferential statistics. The results shows that mothers have adequate knowledge about child sexual abuse (CSA). The recent study shows that mostly mothers have adequate awareness about consequences of child sexual abuse and they stated that CSA cause depression problems that affect academic performance and violent actions. The research shows that mostly mothers didn't know about the laws for child protection and about the social organization serving for abused children. Explanation for such lack of law awareness is limited programs that give awareness about CSA.

Keywords: Knowledge, perception, mothers, child, and sexual abuse.

INTRODUCTION

Child violence is one of the most significant mental health issues. Child violence is one of the most significant social issues impacting children. Child abuse is described as the expected injury to the child. It has been a matter of competent communal concern for decades. Physical and sexual acts were the most widely recognized abuses of

the early period. Popular studies revealed that among women, about 20 percent or 1 in 5 endured sexual harassment in childhood. (Abraham, 2006).

Child sexual abuse (CSA) is a universal communal perpetrator. In this act there is no involvement of a child or the child are unable to give consent about this act as

they do not understand the maltreatment that they are facing at some instant. According to World Health Organization below the age of 18 years 150 million girls and 73 million boys faced sexual violence during their life. The ratio of violence is higher among girls than boys. Incidence is higher among women than among male children. This study indicates 36% female and 29% males have been sexually abused in their childhood. (Mlekwa et al., 2016)

There are a lot of public issues that bother children. Child exploitation is any action that is forcefully done against the child's desire. Child violence has undesirable effects for infants and youth that may spread through adulthood. Some children who are neglected have facing health issues such as hopelessness, alcoholism, substance addiction, smoking, sexual promiscuity, suicide and some prolonged illnesses. Child sexual abuse or child harassment is a type of child abuse in which an older or adult adolescent uses a child for sexual satisfaction. Sexual mistreatment includes acts or behaviors in which an adult, older or more dominant person uses a child for sexual persistence. It involves every touch of sexual determination, breasts, buttocks, genitals, oral sex and sexual contact, showing up to children or attempting to make the child touch them for sexual purposes. Child harassment may happen at different places like residences, home, school and workplace. (Binsha Pappachan et al., 2017)

Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) is a complicated and context-bound phenomenon that exists in all civilizations and there is a substantial rise in recorded cases. Maximum of them is now under the iceberg. Child sexual exploitation has a significant effect on the physical and psychological health, well-being and development of the child over their lifetime. (Mohan, Kochuthresiamma, Joice, and Research, 2017)

Childhood age should be a relaxed time of life full of passion, new worlds to be explored, and cheerful self-mastery and atmosphere. For different children, this is a dream, not a reality. Child violence is one of the greatest severe social problems in the world. Children have their unique advantages of living in a strong civilization, such as being physically and mentally fit, getting medical ease, schooling without and gender discernment. Even outside of this act, children are also neglected in different ways at home. (Swapna, 2019)

Child abuse is any achievement by a new person – mature or children – that lead to severe harm to the child. Sexual mistreatment happens when their dominance or desire to engage a child in sexual activity is used by an adult, stronger child or adolescent. Children on the streets, children at work and children in formal care described the utmost rate of sexual abuse. 50% of the offender is a person well known to the child or in a place of belief and concern. Maximum of children did not mention the issue to someone else. (Kaushik et al., 2017).

Child sexual abuse (CSA) is a thoughtful delinquent who causes both physical and psychosocial harm. Child sexual exploitation is evidence of damaging short-term and long-term punishments that impact children's physical, psychological, social and developmental lives. Maltreated children suffer from despair, anxiety disorder, and nervousness, assertiveness, suicidal rumor, eating disorder, sexual dysfunction, self-protective escape, and social separation that can continue into adulthood. (Alzoubi et al., 2018)

Child sexual abuse (CSA) involves any activity with a child, prior to the age of lawful consent that is to the sexual satisfaction of a mature or significantly older child. It is a substantial violation of fundamental human morality and is liable for a variety of contrary squeals. These involve despair, nervous eating disorders, low self-esteem, posttraumatic anxiety disorder, school/education issues, performance problems including misuse, critical behavior and adult delinquency, and suicide. Sexual acts can include all methods of oral-genital, genital, or anal touch, or child violence that do not require touching, such as exhibitionism, prurience, Or use of the child in the construction of Porn Harm depending on the age and size of the child and the degree of potency used, from CSA varieties. Child sexual abuse may cause internal lacerations and bleeding in serious cases, and internal organ damage can cause death in some cases. (Aboul-Hagag and Hamed, 2012)

Child sexual abuse (CSA) is a type of violence alongside children that is expected to be of great universal concern. The prevalence of child sexual exploitation globally is 18% for girls and 7.6% for boys. The World Health Organization (WHO) has found that one in 13 males and one in five females has had multiple types of sexual harassment despite being a child. (Do et al., 2019)

Disclosure of child sexual abuse is usually late or inadequate, or may not happen at all. Accepting the purposes for disclosure and nondisclosure is significant for parents, detectives, and psychotherapists who offer nourishment for maltreated children throughout the confession method. In a study of over 600 children and teens offering for medical assessments resulting from serious or prolonged abuse, usual time to revelation was 1.5 years and slowest amongst younger sufferers and persons maltreated by their biological parents. Children were more expected to deferral revelation due to distress of their family's responses than fear for their own security. Although demonstrative stress was the most common only motive for confession, collected details concerning outer impacts, such as a wish to defend others, were other common promoters for confession. (Kellogg, 2017)

CSA is related by the Childhood Insufficiencies Directive. Mothers play a vital role in the success of the Sensitivity Directive in their children, especially in younger ages. Nearly 50 percent of mothers of sexually

maltreated children claim that they have been sexually maltreated as children. Subsequently, they are at risk of experiencing considerable grief as a consequence of the exposure of their child's sexual violence. Parents' sorrow will be hampered by their failure to care for and replace the success of the Sentiment Directive in their children. (Langevin, Hébert, Allard-Dansereau, and Bernard-Bonnin, 2016)

Assessment of sexually maltreated children and adolescents must be correct to certify authorized strength and be accomplished with persistence. Analysis of child sexual abuse still depends mostly on the child's assertion of mistreatment, while urogenital analysis produces least medical confirmation of sexual abuse. Officially definite cases of sexual abuse, commonly children do not have physical results investigative of sexual abuse. Consequently, the child's revelation is frequently the most significant part of evidence in defining the probability of abuse. (Aboul-Hagag and Hamed, 2012)

Purpose

The purpose of the research is to evaluate the mother's awareness and understanding of child sexual exploitation.

Significance

The importance of the research is to assess mothers' awareness of child sexual exploitation. The study advises mothers that they can prevent their child from sexual exploitation. The findings obtained in this analysis could be used by other researchers for further studies.

Literature Review

According to Swapna (2019). A study was directed to evaluate the level of responsiveness of child violence among mothers. The study report indicates that mothers' level of knowledge of child abuse and that 30 mothers (15 per cent) had insufficient knowledge and 17 mothers (85 per cent) had moderate knowledge of child abuse.

According to Swapna (2019). Another study conducted to assess awareness of child abuse among mothers in selected areas of Delhi, data showed that the maximum (42%) of mothers are in the age group of 20-25 years and about 28% mothers with the age are 30 years. The majority (44%) of mothers had 2 children, 41% mothers had one child, and merely two per cent were mothers with more than 3 children. The source of learning, the common (69 per cent) of mothers got awareness through newspapers, 59 percent of mothers got knowledge through television, 40 percent of mothers gained knowledge through the internet, and only 27

percent of mothers gained knowledge through school programs.

According to (Alzoubi et al., 2018). A number of studies have shown that CSA meanings for mothers are inadequate to rape and they are unaware that touching and kissing are also a new type of CSA. This restriction and misunderstanding on the concept of Child Sexual Abuse causes mothers to react improperly to sexual assault. They prefer to attention on "rape" through their stoppage teaching and underrate further forms of violence. As a result, the child might be sexually exploited in slight and adequate forms short of the knowledge of their mothers. Contradictions have also been created in parents' understanding of CSA signs and indications. While some parents indicated that they were able to identify the bodily and some behavior symptoms of CSA, others were incapable to identify them.

According to (Alzoubi et al., 2018). (87 per cent of mothers) showed less awareness of the emotional and behavioral signs and symptoms of Child Sexual Abuse in parents. Mothers might play a vital part in Child Sexual Abuse inhibition through reporting, alleviating hazard, counseling and educating on inhibition policies. Many studies have revealed that mothers can counsel their children, teach them about unsafe situations and how to deal with CSA occurrences.

According to (Alzoubi et al., 2018). It is known that mothers who have comprehensive understanding of Child Sexual Abuse efficiently approach well-being events with their children and thereby develop child self-defense skills as opposed to mothers who do not have that knowledge. Mothers' understandings of CSA have a consequence on their awareness of this issue and their attempts to protect their children. Some parents deliberate Child Sexual Abuse to be an unusual occurrence and that their children will not be sexually abused and that there is no need to provide preventive teaching for the child. In a number of research studies, mothers have described the perpetrator as familiar to children, many mothers consider strangers to be a significant source of danger and possible criminals to their children.

According to (Ezzat, 2019). Mothers might show a vital part in preventing child violence by tracking, reducing threat issues, guiding and informing on protective strategies. Many studies have shown that mothers can warn their children, teach them about unsafe environments and how to deal with abuse. It is well identified that mothers who have ample awareness of child abuse effectively discuss protective initiatives with their children and therefore develop child self-protection skills relative to mothers who do not know.

According to (Ezzat, 2019) .In some Arab countries, there is a deficiency of evidence on Arab mothers' knowledge of prevention performs and teaching associated to child violence, and it is also not known whether mothers are essentially educating their children

properly almost abuse, or whether they deliberate it to be an offensive topic. Mothers' habits and attitudes towards child abuse affect their view of this issue and their attempts to defend their child. Parental behaviors are also significant variables for predicting parental neglect. Mothers must take care of their children at all times and note their actions and make them aware of the signs of violence in order to prevent abuse.

According to (Mishra, 2019). Mothers are the main caregivers of children at home. It was found that 90% of mothers had insufficient awareness and did not understand the definition of child violence and were unable to recognize signs and symptoms. If mothers have proper knowledge of child abuse, they will shield their children from abuse and report it on time if it has happened. A lot of negative effects for children's emotional and physical wellbeing can be avoided. The goal of this study is to classify mothers' awareness of child abuse and to assess the correlation of mothers' knowledge levels with selected variables. The results of this study can direct nurses working with mothers to educate them on different aspects of child abuse.

(Gurung and Bahattarai, 2015). The same study showed that only 30% (37% in CDR) of main informants participated assuming that the group and the family had sufficient knowledge of child violence. Of the many parental causes of child abuse, the first explanation is lack of awareness among them. Parents prefer to use punitive forms of corrective action without understanding that it is an assault. Due to lack of awareness, parents, particularly mothers, are reluctant to report cases to the authorities concerned with health care or legal security. If parents have knowledge of child abuse, they can identify signs of child abuse and prevent it from happening by educating the child. The goal of this study was to identify existing knowledge on the issue of child abuse among parents of children under 5 years of age and also to deduce the relationship between selected variables and their level of knowledge.

METHODOLOGY

Research design: The quantitative descriptive cross-sectional research design is used to perform this study.

Place of work: The research was conducted in a children hospital Lahore.

Selected population: The target population for this study is 250 mothers.

Sample size: To calculate the sample size use solvin's

formula.

$$N = N / 1 + N (e)^2$$

$$n = 250 / 1 + 250 (0.05)^2$$

$$n = 250 / 1.6$$

$$n = 156$$

So the study sample is 156 participants.

Data collection: Data was collected through questionnaire distribution among the participants.

Inclusion criteria

The criteria for inclusion include mothers. Mothers who are able to take part in the research report. Participants are available at the time of data collection.

Exclusion criteria

Exclusion requirements include mothers who are not able to take part in our research report. This section also excludes those who are not present at the time of the data collection process.

Ethical consideration

In this research ethical consideration is preferred. For this purpose the permission is obtained from the ethical committee of the University of Lahore, before data collection. Permission is to acquire a written approval from the head of the department of Lahore School of Nursing in the form of consent. Furthermore, informed written and verbal consent is taken before data collection from participants. Participants have the right to leave the study participation at any time. Participants are taken in confidence that all the collected information and records remain confidential.

Tool for data collection

The questionnaire was adopted from the study conducted by Abraham, B. A. (2006). The questionnaire included 23 questions in which 13 questions were about knowledge and 10 questions were about perception of mothers.

1. Demographic information.
2. Knowledge and perception of mothers regarding child sexual abuse.

Data analysis

SPSS version 21 was used to analyze the data. Data analysis was taken up through systematic and logically

techniques (SPSS) after the accomplishment of the data collection process.

Data Analysis Results

In this study 156 questionnaire were distributed to the participant's mothers. It comprises the demographic data and knowledge and perception of the mothers regarding child sexual abuse. Data were analyze through SPSS. Calculated frequencies and percentages are mention in tables and graphs. (Table 1-3)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The aim of the study is to assess mothers' awareness of child sexual exploitation. The study advises mothers that they can prevent their child from sexual exploitation. The findings obtained in this analysis could be used by other researchers for further studies. The objectives of this study are: 1. Assess mothers' awareness and understanding of child sexual exploitation. 2. Finding a connection between mothers' awareness and the selected baseline results.

The ages of the participants are 20-25 is 14.1%. 26-30 44.2%. 31-40 41.7%. The educational level of the participants are Primary 9.6%. Secondary 37.8%. Post-secondary (n= 82) 52.6%. Occupation level of the participants are Employment 63.5%. Unemployment (n= 57) 36.5%.

In this study the participants 92.9% answered True, (n= 11) 7.1% participants answered false to this question: The problem of CSA has physical, social and psychological negative consequences. 80.8% participants answered True and 19.2% participants answered False to this question: There are mandatory laws that protect children from CSA. The participants 78.8% answered true and 21.2% participants answered False to this question: There are social organizations that provide services for children exposed to CSA. 89.7% participants answered True and 10.3% participants answered False to this question: If a child has been sexually abused, there will usually be no obvious physical evidence. The participants 95.5% answered true and 4.5% participants answered False to this question: Men sexually abuse children in most cases. In this study 90.4% participants answered true and 9.6% participants answered False to this question: Educated mothers know more about CSA than non-educated or uneducated mothers. The participants 91.0% answered true and 9.0% participants answered False to the question: Mothers educate their children about CSA more than fathers. 78.2% participants answered True and 21.8% answered False to the question: The children should be taught about CSA at an early age. 67.3% participants answered True and 32.7% participants answered False to the question: A person

who has sexually abused a child will likely repeat the offense. The participants 84.6% answered True and 32.7% participants answered False to the question: Children's education about CSA can prevent CSA. 80.1% participants answered True and 19.9% participants answered False to the question: All children who report or disclose CSA telling the truth. 93.6% participants answered True and 6.4% participants answered False to the question: Mother's knowledge about CSA can prevent the CSA. The participants 57.7% answered True and 42.3% participants answered False to the question: The child who was sexually abused will be held back from disclosing the episode by the abuser. The participants' 93.6% answer agree to this statement: CSA is a common problem in our society. Other participants 2.6% respond disagree and 3.8% participants answer not sure. The participants 42.3% answer agree to the statement: sexual abuses are only serious when it involves intercourse. Other participants 51.9% responded disagree and % participants were not sure. 46.2% participants answer agree to the statement: Homosexual abuses are more serious than heterosexual abuse. Other participants 34.0% responded disagree and 19.9% participants were not sure. The participants 75.0% answer agree to the statement: The child who was sexually abused is not to be blamed. Other participants 10.9% responded disagree and 14.1% participants were not sure. The participants 66.0% answer agree to the statement: Most sexual abuse is committed by someone the child knows and trusts. Other participants 22.4% responded disagree and 11.5% participants were not sure. 75.6% participants agree to the statement: Female adults cannot sexually abuse children. Other participants 3.8% responded disagree and 20.5% participants were not sure. The participants 69.2% answer agree to the statement: Boys also can be sexually abused. Other participants 14.1% responded disagree and 16.7% participants were not sure. The participants' 31.4% answer agree to the statement: It is only wayward children who are sexually abused. Other participants 50.6% respond disagree and 17.9% participants were not sure. 53.2% participants answer to the statement: My child can never be sexually abused. Other participants 34.6% responded disagree and 12.2% participants were not sure. The participants 30.8% answer agree to the statement: Discussing sex with children is bad for them. Other participants 50.0% responded disagree and 19.2% were not sure.

According to (Alzoubi et al., 2018). The results shows that mothers have adequate knowledge about child sexual abuse (CSA). The recent study shows that mostly mothers have adequate awareness about consequences of child sexual abuse and they stated that CSA cause depression problems that affect academic performance and violent actions. The research shows that mostly mothers didn't know about the laws for child protection and about the social organization serving for abused children. Explanation for such lack of law awareness

Table 1. Demographic information of participants.

S.no			Frequency	Percent
1.1	Age	20-25	22	14.1
		26-30	69	44.2
		31-40	65	41.7
		Total	165	100
1.2	Educational level	Primary	15	9.6
		Secondary	59	37.8
		Post-secondary	82	52.6
		Total	156	100
1.3	Occupation	Employment	99	63.5
		Unemployment	57	36.5
		Total	156	100

Table 2. Mothers knowledge about child sexual abuse (CSA).

S.No	Questions		Frequency	Percentage
2.1	The problem of CSA have physical, social and psychological negative consequences.	True	145	92.9%
		False	11	7.1%
		Total	156	100%
2.2	There are mandatory laws that protect children from CSA.	True	49	31.4%
		False	107	68.6%
		Total	156	100%
2.3	There are social organizations that provide services for children exposed to CSA.	True	54	34.6%
		False	102	56.4%
		Total	156	100%
2.4	If a child has been sexually abused, there will usually be no obvious physical evidence.	True	140	89.7%
		False	16	10.3%
		Total	156	100%
2.5	Men sexually abuse children in most cases.	True	149	95.5%
		False	7	4.5%
		Total	156	100%
2.6	Educated mothers know about CSA than non-educated or uneducated mothers.	True	141	90.4%
		False	15	9.6%
		Total	156	100%
2.7	Mothers educate their children about CSA more than fathers.	True	142	91.0%
		False	14	9.0%
		Total	156	100%
2.8	The children should be taught about CSA in early age.	True	122	78.2%
		False	34	21.8%
		Total	156	100%
2.9	A person who has sexually abused a child will likely repeat the offense.	True	105	67.3%
		False	51	32.7%
		Total	156	100%
2.10	Children's education about CSA can prevent CSA.	True	132	84.6%
		False	24	15.4%
		Total	156	100%
2.11	All children who report or disclose CSA telling the truth.	True	125	80.1%
		False	31	19.9%
		Total	156	100%
2.12	Mother's knowledge about CSA can prevent the CSA.	True	146	93.6%
		False	10	6.4%
		Total	156	100%

Table 2. Continue

2.13	The child who was sexually abused will be held back from disclosing the episode by the abuser.	True	90	57.7%
		False	66	42.3%
		Total	156	100%

Table 3. Mothers perception regarding child sexual abuse (CSA).

S.No	Questions		Frequency	Percentage
3.1	CSA is a common problem in our society.	Agree	146	93.6%
		Disagree	4	2.6%
		Not sure	6	3.8%
		Total	156	100%
3.2	Sexual abuses are only serious when it involves intercourse.	Agree	66	42.3%
		Disagree	81	51.9%
		Not sure	9	5.8%
		Total	156	100%
3.3	Homosexual abuses are more serious than heterosexual abuse.	Agree	72	46.2%
		Disagree	53	34.0%
		Not sure	31	19.9%
		Total	156	100%
3.4	The child who was sexually abused is not be blamed.	Agree	117	75.0%
		Disagree	17	10.9%
		Not sure	22	14.1%
		Total	156	100%
3.5	Most sexual abuse is committed by someone the child knows and trusts.	Agree	103	66.0%
		Disagree	35	22.4%
		Not sure	18	11.5%
		Total	156	100%
3.6	Female adults cannot sexually abuse children.	Agree	118	75.6%
		Disagree	6	3.8%
		Not sure	32	20.5%
		Total	156	100%
3.7	Boys also can be sexually abused.	Agree	108	69.2%
		Disagree	22	14.1%
		Not sure	26	16.7%
		Total	156	100%
3.8	It is only wayward children who are sexually abused.	Agree	49	31.4%
		Disagree	79	50.6%
		Not sure	28	17.9%
		Total	156	100%
3.9	My child can never be sexually abused.	Agree	83	53.2%
		Disagree	54	34.6%
		Not sure	19	12.2%
		Total	156	100%
3.10	Discussing sex with children is bad for them.	Agree	48	30.8%
		Disagree	78	50.0%
		Not sure	30	19.2%
		Total	156	100%

is limited programs that give awareness about CSA. According to (Mohan et al., 2017). Conducted a study

whose results showed that most probable children were abused by the known people. 67% of respondents gave

this response. Research in Chennai shows that 71.8% respondents respond that most of the time children are abused by strangers. It was also believed that boys were less sexually abused as compared to girls. 54% respondents give this response about boys and 74% respondents respond about girl's sexual abuse. 90% mothers had less knowledge and positive attitude to tell their children about CSA. 10.8% of mothers did not guide their children about sexual abuse. They thought that if they guide their children about CSA, their children will come to know about sex. On the other hand, 65.6% of mothers thought that children should learn about good and bad touch.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The aim of this study is evaluate the knowledge and perception of mothers towards child sexual abuse. This study followed a quantitative approach and exploratory design to analyse the identified variables. This study represents that mothers have adequate knowledge about child sexual abuse (CSA) and mostly mothers have adequate awareness about consequences of child sexual abuse as they stated that CSA cause depression problems that affect academic performance and violent actions. Mostly mothers showed that they didn't know about the laws for child protection and about the social organization serving for abused children. Explanation for such lack of law awareness is limited programs that give awareness about CSA. Knowledge and perceptions of mothers is important factor for prevention of child sexual abuse (CSA). Study results shows that mothers should educate about child sexual abuse, sign and symptoms of child sexual abuse and probable lawbreakers. Here is a requirement for attention to improve the awareness of mothers who have low level of education to enhance the awareness and perception about child sexual abuse (CSA) and its preventive measures.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Knowledge and perceptions of mothers is important factor for prevention of child sexual abuse (CSA).
- Study results shows that mothers should educate about child sexual abuse, sign and symptoms of child sexual abuse and probable lawbreakers.
- Here is a requirement for attention to improve the awareness of mothers who have low level of teaching to enhance the awareness and perception about child sexual abuse (CSA) and its preventive measures.
- There is a need to focus on low family income mothers.
- The government should introduce new policies for prevention of child sexual abuse, and should distribute pamphlets regarding information and awareness about

CSA among mothers in various settings like clinics, workplace and health care centers.

- There should be established some prevention programs in school courses that would be very helpful for prevention of CSA.
- The organizations that offer assistance in CSA cases can use TV and Newspaper to give awareness on CSA.

LIMITATIONS

Limitations of this study enlisted are as following:

- Unwillingness and hesitation of the participants were seen during collection of data.
- The problem I faced most of the time during the completing the questionnaire was limitation of time.
- As the research was conducted on small samples so for a similar population we can't generalize it.
- For the larger generalization, data could be taken from more than one sample.
- As standardized tools were not accessible so the researcher had to make tools to conduct the study.

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